

Data by experience: A survey investigating differences in data citation practices according to researchers' career stages

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Abstract

In this paper, we present the results of the largest known survey (n=2,492) to explicitly investigate data citation practices, preferences, and motivations for indicating data reuse, using a sample of academic authors by career stage. We present findings about researchers' current practices and motivations for reusing and citing data and also examine their preferences for how they would like their own data to be cited. Key findings include: 1) researchers of various career stages have similar views and behaviors towards data sharing and reuse; 2) most sharing and reuse patterns increased or decreased consistently along with career progression; 3) early career researchers place more importance on metrics about data created by others while 4) middle career researchers place more importance on metrics for their own data. Additionally, we discuss the unique qualities within each career stage, and present a future outlook on how research on this topic can be carried forward.

Keywords: career stage, data citation, research data, data reuse, data sharing, open science, survey

1. Introduction

A researcher's career stage (i.e., the number of years active in academia), is important to consider when evaluating the general research practices of individual researchers. Specifically, when it comes to referring to data as research outputs (a relatively new phenomenon), the stage at which a researcher is at in their career is likely to have certain implications. This relationship between data citation practices and career stages has not been well documented via scientometric approaches, and as such we do not know if and how these practices vary.

As individual evaluation becomes increasingly important in an effort to understand the roles and positions occupied by researchers (Glänzel, 2014), career stage is an increasingly important factor (Lu et al., 2021). As Stephan and Levin argue, the career stage of a researcher is particularly impactful because the reward structure in science "places great emphasis on the attainment of benchmarks in the context of a career" (2001, p. 685). As a result, researchers may have different motivations, expectations, goals, and roles at various stages during their careers (Niles et al., 2020). For instance, the position of an author's name on an authors list in a scientific

article often reflects their career stage (Milojević et al., 2018). Similarly, the pressure to publish may be felt differently by researchers at different stages of their careers (Armond & Kakuk, 2023). Furthermore, it has been shown that the career stage of researchers can impact open science practices and attitudes towards open science, such as data sharing and reuse (Toribio-Flórez et al., 2021).

Data sharing and reuse are important components of open science that can enable transparency, democratize and accelerate research, and help avoid duplication of effort. (Baker, 2016; Borgman & Brand, 2024; National Institutes of Health, 2023; Pasquetto et al., 2017). Despite the importance of data sharing and reuse, the ability to trace data in scientific works/publications is notoriously difficult to accomplish (Lane et al., 2020; van de Sandt et al., 2019), in part because standards for data citation are lacking or strongly dependent on disciplinary norms. While attempts have been made to overcome this issue using a variety of approaches (Ninkov et al., 2021; Park & Wolfram, 2017), the lack of a persistent and data citation mechanism (Chavan & Ingwersen, 2009; Ingwersen & Chavan, 2011) makes conducting large scale and representative scientometric studies on this issue difficult. Such studies require “a more profound understanding of the norms regulating the citation of data and analyzing author citation behavior” (Silvello, 2018, p. 17). In this paper, we therefore adopt a survey method to examine the relationship between career stage and data citation practices with a goal to determine whether and how career stage impacts data citation practices

This paper analyzes how researchers in different career stages cite, share and reuse data as well as how they prefer to have the reuse of their own data be indicated and what types of recognition and reward they would expect for data sharing. We surveyed 2,492 researchers about their data citation practices, preferences and motivations for indicating data reuse, using a representative sample of authors (as represented in the Web of Science) by discipline. While disciplinary differences were addressed in a previous paper (Gregory, Ninkov, Ripp, et al., 2023), this paper focuses specifically on variations between data citation and reuse practices between career stages.

2. Background

Among the socio-demographic factors that influence academics' research practices as well as how they are evaluated, career stages have been identified as an important variable (Niles et al., 2020; Stephan & Levin, 2001). The academic career can be viewed as a research trail (Chubin & Connolly, 1982). It is an accumulation of research activities that can be traced and analyzed throughout one's career. Also, as researchers transition from one project to another, their role within research projects as well as the scientific community at large evolves. They move from apprentice status, where they conduct research under the direction of supervisors, to colleagues, where they conduct independent research, and finally to supervisor status, where they train and direct apprentices (Laudel & Gläser, 2008). In parallel, researchers will also hold specific positions within research organizations that come with task definitions, salaries, and performance expectations (Laudel & Gläser, 2008). As researchers progress through different career stages, changes can be observed in their research and publication practices. These changes are associated with specific career stages and include the time allocated for teaching, research, or administrative tasks, as well as publication activities, productivity, the choice of research subjects, and the role played in collaboration networks (Drennan et al., 2013; Glänzel, 2014; Höhle & Teichler, 2013; Robinson-Garcia et al., 2020). Finally, changes in practices are closely linked to the development of skills and the impact of productivity incentives. For instance, early career researchers (ECRs) acquire more new skills than senior researchers, and they are more strongly influenced by productivity incentives (Dietz et al., 2000).

2.1. Researchers' career stages and age

Due to their impact on research practices, bibliometric studies consider career stages as an important variable (Zhang & Glänzel, 2012) to provide individual context to bibliometric measurements (Glänzel, 2014). Indeed, career stage is a central factor in bibliometric studies due to its influence on authorial practices (Costas & Bordons, 2011), scientific collaborations (Hu et al., 2014; Lu et al., 2021; Zeng et al., 2016), geographic mobility (Cañibano et al., 2020), and productivity (Falagas et al., 2008; Levin & Stephan, 1989).

Career progression is measured either by a researcher's age or their career stage and the two concepts are sometimes used synonymously. Since age is usually not available in the scholarly

databases from which the metadata needed for bibliometric analyses are extracted, bibliometricians distinguish between the biological and academic age of researchers, using the year of the first publication of an author as a proxy for their academic age (Kwiek & Roszka, 2022; Nane et al., 2017). The term career length is also used to identify the difference between the year of publication of a scholar's first paper and the year of analysis (Radicchi & Castellano, 2013).

In studies where it is possible to directly engage with researchers, for example through questionnaires or interviews, it is easier to receive first-hand information on age and career stage instead of proxies. When examining study outcomes related to age or career stages, inconsistencies in approaches and insufficient detail on calculation processes hinder comparability across research utilizing researcher career stages as a variable. Furthermore, the absence of a standardized scale for describing these stages adds complexity to the comparison. Some ask researchers to identify themselves as early, mid, and late career (Hrynaszkiewicz et al., 2021), or ask for the number of years since starting their Ph.D. (Khan et al., 2023). Others combine current employment status with a categorization of career stages. For example, Campbell et al. (2019) propose a classification based on years since completion of a PhD: an ECR (<5 years post-PhD), a mid-career researcher (MCR) (>5 and <10 years post-PhD), or a late-career researcher (LCR) (>10 years post-PhD, heading a research institution and/or laboratory). Such classifications are further complicated by the fact that academic careers progress differently in different countries and academic systems (Ates & Brechelmacher, 2013).

2.2. Career stages and data citation, sharing and reuse

Among the research practices influenced by career stages are data sharing, reuse and citation practices, which are becoming increasingly important as the emphasis on open research grows. Findings from the few studies that have examined this issue, mostly using questionnaires, vary in terms of perceptions, motivations, and applications of these practices at different career stages. The lack of knowledge about the motivations for citing data (Silvello, 2018) is not addressed in most of the studies presented below, which mostly focus on data sharing practices. We synthesize these studies here and present their results by career stage. Also, we acknowledge the impact of disciplinary cultures on research practices, particularly in regard to data sharing and reuse. Since

Gregory, Ninkov, Ripp, et al. (2023) already analyzed discipline in detail, this paper focuses on the impact of career stage on data-related practices. However, it should be noted that a significant portion of the reviewed literature presented below on data-related practices is concentrated on researchers in the natural or medical sciences.

2.2.1. Early-career researchers

Several studies agree that ECRs have positive perceptions of data sharing (Karadkar et al., 2022; Koch et al., 2018; Tenopir et al., 2015; Toribio-Flórez et al., 2021), but are less likely to share their data (Abele-Brehm et al., 2019; Chawinga & Zinn, 2019; Tenopir et al., 2011; Zhu, 2020). One possible explanation for the contrast between positive perceptions and low uptake of data sharing is that young researchers place more importance on the recognition and control of their data (Tenopir et al., 2015). Due to the pressure to publish research articles, which is particularly pronounced for ECRs looking for employment, they see more value in keeping their data private to publish about them (Dorta-González et al., 2021; Gewin, 2016; Lantian, 2021; Schmidt et al., 2016). Also, fear of being scooped or other data misuse seems to affect young researchers more than their senior colleagues (Abele-Brehm et al., 2019; Barlösius, 2023; Soeharjono & Roche, 2021). Similarly, the lack of policies mandating data sharing has been identified as an important reason to explain the lack of data sharing among ECRs (Nicholas et al., 2020). At the same time, ECRs are the ones who most value citation of their data, and this is a motivating factor for sharing their data (Dorta-González et al., 2021).

Some studies show opposite results. In a study of data sharing practices among astrophysicists, younger researchers were more likely to share their data, although there was no consensus among respondents on the influence of academic position on motivations to share or not share data (Zuiderwijk & Spiers, 2019). Campbell and colleagues (2019) contacted 479 corresponding authors responsible for 771 manuscripts published by Australian institutions between 1995 and 2015 to request data sharing. They were surprised to find that students and ECRs were more inclined to share data compared to more experienced researchers. In a study surveying nearly 1,500 young researchers from several disciplines, Nicholas and colleagues (2020) found that 37.2% of those who had produced data had shared it. Andrea and colleagues (2021) found that

the more recently researchers started their Ph.D., the more likely they are to publish their first data set within 5 years.

2.2.2. Mid-career researchers

MCRs have been less studied in the literature on data sharing practices, which often focus on ECRs (Karadkar et al., 2022; Koch et al., 2018; Nicholas et al., 2020; Toribio-Flórez et al., 2021) or on the comparison between ECRs and LCRs (Barlösius, 2023; Campbell et al., 2019; Curty et al., 2017; Dorta-González et al., 2021). Even when they are included in studies, MCRs exhibit less clear behaviors and perceptions of data sharing than ECRs or LCRs and are therefore either absent from results or only mentioned in passing (Khan et al., 2023; Linek et al., 2017; Schmidt et al., 2016; Tenopir et al., 2015). Specifically, Tenopir et al. (2015) found that MCRs were more willing to share data with a broad group of researchers and emphasized the importance of citing datasets. Hrynaskiewicz and colleagues (2021) asked respondents divided into three career stages (early, mid and late) to rate the importance and their satisfaction for 36 factors related to sharing or reusing data. They discovered that ECRs and MCRs faced challenges in discovering and accessing data and would like to spend less time making individual data requests and searching for articles with reusable datasets. Finally, Abele-Brehm and colleagues (2019) identified that researchers not yet occupying a tenured position will experience more fears regarding data sharing and other practices.

2.2.3. Late-career researchers

LCRs are often identified as the group of researchers who share their data the most (Chawinga & Zinn, 2019; Dorta-González et al., 2021; Khan et al., 2023; Linek et al., 2017). Chawinga et Zinn (2019) argue that this situation may be explained by the fact that experienced researchers, thanks to their experience, produce reliable and high-quality data that are potentially more used by other researchers. From the point of view of motivations to share their data, more experienced researchers would be more inclined to see data sharing as a moral and professional obligation (Milia et al., 2012). In fact, they are more likely than other career stages to share their data without restrictions (Tenopir et al., 2011). More experienced researchers have also been identified as the group that values citation of their data by other researchers the least (Dorta-González et al., 2021), probably because the credit gained from such citations is less

relevant at the end of their career. Instead, they would be motivated by a desire to ensure the longevity of their research, which includes sharing data and promoting a culture of open data (Tenopir et al., 2015).

3. Methods and Data

In this section, we will briefly describe the methodology for surveying researchers. A more detailed description, in particular of the recruitment strategy and aim of creating a sample representative across academic disciplines, is available in Gregory et al., 2022 and in Gregory, Ninkov, Ripp, et al., 2023, which focused on disciplinary differences between researchers and their data reuse and citation practices. This study analyzes differences of data sharing, reuse and citation with regard to researchers' career stages.

3.1. Questionnaire, sampling, recruitment, and response

The questionnaire used in this study (Gregory et al., 2022) was designed and scripted in SurveyMonkey. This questionnaire adopted a branching design with 2 primary branches (reusers of data and non-reusers of data) and consisted of three sections (Reusing and Citing Data; Rewarding Data Management; Demographics). The questions were either binary, multiple choice, 5-point likert scale, multiple response, or open-ended. Additionally, some questions consisted of several options that could be selected, which could also be thought of as sub-questions. Our population of interest consisted of a diverse range of researchers across disciplines and career stages who have published a paper indexed in Web of Science between 2016 and 2020. In total, we received 3,632 responses, 2,509 of which were complete. After cleaning the data for entry system errors, the survey had a total of 2,492 responses and a completion rate of 68.6% for a corrected response rate of 1.6%.

One of the questions included in the demographic section of the survey asked researchers to select one of the following categories to indicate their professional experience in terms of number of years of experience: 0 to 5 years, 6 to 15 years, 16 to 30 years and 30+ years. These categories were drawn from a career stage classification used in a previous survey investigating data discovery practices in research (Gregory et al., 2020). Given the lack of standardization in career stage categories, which, as noted above, vary across disciplines and countries, we

propose, in Table 1 below, a label for each career stage, which was not shown to participants, as well as a non-exhaustive list of what we envision are possible positions that might be included in each of these stages.

Years of experience	Label for career stage	Example positions
0-5 years	Early career researchers (ECRs)	Masters or PhD Students
6-15 years	Mid-early career researchers (MECRs)	PhD Students, postdoctoral fellows, pre-tenure faculty, junior researchers
16-30 years	Mid-late career researchers (MLCRs)	Pre-tenure faculty, tenured faculty, senior researchers
30+ years	Late career researchers (LCRs)	Tenured faculty, senior researchers

Table 1. Label and example positions associated with various career stages based on years of experience

Data were analyzed using Excel and SPSS. Normality testing indicated the use of non-parametric tests for significance. As such, for questions on differences between nominal variables, Chi-Squared Tests were done and the percentages were reported. For questions on differences between continuous variables, Kruskal-Wallis H Test was conducted and mean rank was reported.

In our previous paper, which analyzed the results of this survey with regard to disciplinary differences (Gregory, Ninkov, Ripp, et al., 2023), we generated a weight to transform our sample to accurately reflect the distribution of researchers in the Web of Science by discipline. In this paper, an additional weighting was applied in order to avoid overrepresentation of participants from certain career stages and disciplines. Since the true distribution of career stages by discipline is unknown, we opted to create the known distribution of disciplines (according to the OECD Fields of Science and Technology classification) in the Web of Science within each career stage. As such, for each of the 4 career stages, a weight for each of the 6 disciplines of the OECD classification was assigned. This resulted in 24 different weights applied that made each career

stage have the disciplinary distribution equal to that of the population. This new variable representing the frequency weighted by both discipline and career stage was added to a second version of the dataset containing the survey answers (Ninkov et al., 2023).

3.2. Limitations

This study methodology has limitations regarding the potential for sampling bias. Most importantly, as we recruited participants via email addresses of corresponding authors, it is most likely that senior researchers (i.e., LCRs) who usually occupy this role (Chinchilla-Rodríguez et al., 2024) are overrepresented in our sample. As such, there is uncertainty about the representativeness of the career stage divisions of our sample. Additionally, since the true distribution of researchers by career stage by discipline is unknown, this has led to a challenge in weighting the sample properly to reflect the reality of academia. As such, we believe there is a bias against early career researchers because of this issue of corresponding authors.

As noted in detail previously (Gregory, Ninkov, Ripp, et al., 2023), our sample will also have bias as it was developed based on journals that have been published in the Web of Science, a database that has its own biases (Gusenbauer, 2022). Additionally, because the survey was conducted in English, there is a certain bias that will be generated by only asking researchers comfortable enough to respond in English. For example, we believe because of these limitations, there will be an underrepresentation of researchers from the Humanities and from the Global South (Mongeon & Paul-Hus, 2016; Petr et al., 2021; Sugimoto & Larivière, 2018).

3.3. Ethics and data availability

We received ethical approval from University of Ottawa for the study under number S-08-21-7283. The anonymized data from this survey are available under a CC-BY-4.0 license (Ninkov et al., 2023).

4. Findings

While there are several significant differences found between the different career stages, it is important to begin with an important overall finding: researchers at the various career stages responded similarly to most of the questions in the questionnaire. Of the 85 total

questions/sub-questions, 51 (60.0%) found no significant difference between career stages. The general descriptives of these questions from the survey have been discussed previously in detail (Gregory, Ninkov, Ripp, et al., 2023). The similarities found between the career stages in this study can help us understand the existence of a certain homogeneity among researchers of all stages in their career and data practices. For example, regardless of career stage, the majority of responders to the survey are reusing data (81.3%).

The vast majority of respondents work in universities or research institutions located in North America or Europe/Central Asia. With regard to gender, roughly two-thirds of respondents self-identify as men (66.2%), one-third are women (31.5%), and the remainder selected non-binary, prefer not to say, or an option not listed (2.3%). Additionally, with regard to career stage (see Figure 1), the majority of the respondents in our survey were from the mid (MECRs, MLCRs) to late career stages (LCRs). Early career stage researchers (ECRs) were the most difficult group to reach, accounting for 6.3% of total responses. This is most likely due to our recruitment strategy, which targeted corresponding authors, a role that is less often occupied by ECRs (Chinchilla-Rodríguez et al., 2024).

Figure 1. Percentage of respondents by career stage

The following four sections will break down the significant findings into four components: i) data sharing and reuse; ii) data citation practices; iii) respondents' preferences for their own data

and iv) recognition and reward. It is important to note that these results are based on the weighted number of respondents per discipline and career stage as mentioned in the methodology.

4.1. Sharing and reuse

Figure 2 summarizes statistically significant results from questions related to data sharing and reuse practices. First, ECRs are significantly less likely to say they have shared their own research data (68.2%) or have used their own data multiple times (65.6%). This progressively gets more common in each of the later career stages, with 85.6% of the LCRs sharing their data and 77.7% reusing their data multiple times.

Question	Measurement value	ECRs	MECRs	MLCRs	LCRS	Comparison value
Sharing and reusing your own research data						
Q20. Have you ever shared your own research data?	Percent that selected this option	68.2%	78.3%	80.8%	85.6%	80.4%
Q21. Have you ever used your own data multiple times?	Percent that selected this option	65.6%	71.5%	72.6%	77.7%	73.1%
Q4. How frequently do you reuse secondary data:						
as a model, algorithm, or system input?	Mean rank (total = 2026)	1095.8	1051.8	1013.8	971.5	1013
to calibrate instruments or models?	Mean rank (total = 2026)	1092.9	1073.9	1014.2	944.0	1013
Q13. What are your reasons for not reusing data created by other people:						
you cannot find the data you need?	Percent that selected this option	31.6%	15.5%	17.5%	12.0%	16.8%
you do not know how to give credit for data created by other people?	Percent that selected this option	26.5%	9.9%	9.6%	10.0%	11.1%

Figure 2. Summary of statistically significant results by discipline for questions related to data sharing and reuse. Blue indicates a result greater than the average of the reporting statistic for each question; red indicates a result less than the average. Darker shades indicate larger deviation from the average. Options where career stages did not show statistically significant differences are not shown.

Next, when reusing data, early career researchers were significantly more likely to say that they did so as a model, algorithm, or system input (see Figure 3) or to calibrate instruments (see Figure 4). ECRs are the most likely to say they reuse data for these purposes, and again the pattern progresses directionally to the later career stage who are the least likely to say they do so.

Figure 3. Summary of distribution of frequency to reuse data as model, algorithm, or system input (Q4.4) by career stage ($n = 2,026$). Bars are arranged around the middle (50.0% mark) of the ‘sometimes’ category.

Figure 4. Summary of distribution of frequency to reuse data to calibrate instruments or models (Q4.5) by career stage ($n = 2,026$). Bars are arranged around the middle (50.0% mark) of the ‘sometimes’ category.

With regard to why researchers do not reuse data, two significant differences were identified between career stages: they cannot find the data they need and they do not know how to give

credit. As we can see in Figure 4, while in general researchers did not indicate that this was this case, ECRs were more likely to select both of these responses than the other groups, with 26.0%-32.0% indicating this was the case vs. 10.0-17.0% for the other groups.

Figure 4. Summary of distribution of frequency for why researchers do not cite data by career stage ($n = 466$).

4.2. Citation practices

Figure 5 summarizes statistically significant results from questions related to citation practices. First, when it comes to what is cited when data is reused, a significant difference was observed between the career stages and citing the source of the data. ECRs were the least likely to say they cite the source of the data (67.8%), with a directional increase by experience, with the LCRs indicating they did this the most (74.6% said they did so).

With regard to how researchers cite data, a significant difference was also observed when it comes to including the citation to data in a reference list. Again, ECRs were the least likely to indicate they did this (69.4%), with the LCRs indicating they did this the most frequently (79.4%).

Question	Measurement value	ECRs	MECRs	MLCRs	LCRs	Comparison value
Q5. When you reuse data, do you usually cite or reference:						
the source of the data?	Mean rank (total = 2026)	943.7	979.0	1026.8	1083.2	1013
Q6. When you reuse data, how do you cite or reference them?						
including a citation to data in reference lists	Mean rank (total = 2026)	994.9	987.1	988.0	1115.2	1013
Q12. Do you ever cite data for the following reason?						
to correct your own data (you cite your own data)	Percent that selected this option	15.7%	17.4%	22.6%	24.0%	21.0%
to build on or use data you have created (you cite your own data)	Percent that selected this option	44.1%	52.2%	56.4%	63.0%	56.1%
to criticize or correct the data of others	Percent that selected this option	16.8%	21.1%	27.1%	35.3%	26.7%
none of the above	Percent that selected this option	46.5%	35.0%	30.8%	22.5%	30.9%
Q18. Are you aware of and do you use the following recommendations:						
citation style guides	Percent that selected aware and use this option	70.7%	66.0%	58.6%	50.0%	59.6%

Figure 5. Summary of statistically significant results from questions related to citation practices. Blue indicates a result greater than the average of the reporting statistic for each question; red indicates a result less than the average. Darker shades indicate larger deviation from the average. Options where career stages did not show statistically significant differences are not shown.

As shown in Figures 5 and 6, significant differences were also found with regard to motivation to cite data. This included a variety of reasons, including to correct your own data, to build on data you created or to criticize others, as well as the option that “none of the above” were motivations to cite data. LCRs were more likely to select one or all of these options while ECRs more frequently opted for “none of the above”. Each of these four results followed the directional pattern observed from early to late career researchers (i.e., progression in the middle career stages towards the one end or the other).

Figure 6. Summary of statistically significant results from questions related to reasons for citing data ($n = 1,884$).

Additionally, a significant difference was observed between the career stages and their awareness and use of citation style guides for data citation. ECRs were the most likely to be aware and use these standards (70.7%) while LCRs the least likely to be aware of the standards at all (50.0%).

4.3. Preferences for own data

Figure 7 summarizes statistically significant results from questions related to researchers preferences for when others cite their data.

Question	Measurement value	ECRs	MECRs	MLCRs	LCRs	Comparison value
Q8. What would you prefer that other people cite/reference when they use your data?						
an article or publication analyzing the data	Percent that selected this option	85.3%	80.9%	85.9%	86.0%	84.3%
a data paper	Percent that selected this option	34.2%	32.5%	31.0%	25.6%	30.3%
Q9. How would you prefer other people to cite/reference your data?						
mentioning data in captions figures or tables	Percent that selected this option	38.1%	36.4%	41.7%	44.4%	40.4%

Figure 7. Summary of statistically significant results from questions related to researchers preferences for when others cite their data. Blue indicates a result greater than the average of the reporting statistic for each question; red indicates a result less than the average. Darker shades indicate larger deviation from the average. Options where career stages did not show statistically significant differences are not shown.

When it comes to *what* they prefer that other researchers cite when they cite their data, a difference between career stages was observed for an article or publication analyzing the data as well as a data paper. While the majority of researchers across career stages would like others to cite a publication analyzing the data, MCRs were the least likely to choose this option, (80.9%) while the other three groups more frequently said this was what they preferred (85.3%-86.3%). With regard to citing a data paper (a fairly new phenomenon), LCR were the least likely to select this option (25.6%) while ECRs were the most (34.2%).

As for how researchers preferred other people to cite or reference their data, a significant difference was observed for mentioning data in the captions of figures or tables. MCRs were the least likely to select this option (36.4%) while LCRs selected it the most frequently (44.4%).

4.4. Recognition and reward of data practices

Figure 8 summarizes statistically significant results from questions related to researchers preferences for rewarding data practices. First, with regard to rewarding the creation of good data documents and workflows, a significant difference was also observed between the career stages. MCRs indicated this was the most important (82.6% indicating extremely important or important), while LCRs were the least (71.7% indicating extremely important or important).

Question	Measurement value	ECRs	MECRs	MLCRs	LCRs	Comparison value
Q19+22 How important is it to you to:						
to have the creation of good data documentation and workflows be rewarded	Mean rank (total - 2492)	1280.9	1325.0	1255.2	1157.8	1246
assess the reach and influence of your own data?	Mean rank (total - 2492)	1300.9	1292.3	1259.2	1189.2	1246
assess the reach and influence of other people's data which you reuse?	Mean rank (total - 2492)	1366.9	1289.2	1227.1	1221.4	1246
Q23. How important would it be for you to know the following information about others' data which you may potential reuse:						
the number of citations the data have received	Mean rank (total - 2492)	1401.2	1357.7	1222.7	1128.6	1246
the number of times the data have been downloaded?	Mean rank (total - 2492)	1423.8	1355.8	1211.5	1141.0	1246
the number of times the data have been viewed?	Mean rank (total - 2492)	1438.0	1331.0	1210.7	1170.5	1246
information about where the data were used?	Mean rank (total - 2492)	1441.2	1328.8	1251.9	1112.6	1246
descriptions or a narrative providing details about how the data were used?	Mean rank (total - 2492)	1472.3	1326.8	1252.6	1105.2	1246
information about who has used the data?	Mean rank (total - 2492)	1327.0	1296.7	1264.4	1168.4	1246
if the data have received recognition outside the scholarly system?	Mean rank (total - 2492)	1421.4	1344.3	1244.9	1108.1	1246
Q24. How important would it be for you to know the following information about your data:						
the number of citations the data have received	Mean rank (total - 2492)	1212.3	1347.1	1275.8	1118.3	1246
the number of times the data have been downloaded?	Mean rank (total - 2492)	1251.6	1353.8	1259.6	1122.1	1246
the number of times the data have been viewed?	Mean rank (total - 2492)	1298.3	1343.0	1247.7	1141.4	1246
information about where the data were used?	Mean rank (total - 2492)	1366.3	1318.9	1287.4	1094.8	1246
descriptions or a narrative providing details about how the data were used?	Mean rank (total - 2492)	1433.1	1334.2	1272.5	1077.6	1246
information about who has used the data?	Mean rank (total - 2492)	1286.3	1287.8	1283.8	1163.3	1246
if the data have received recognition outside the scholarly system?	Mean rank (total - 2492)	1357.5	1364.0	1291.8	1031.9	1246

Figure 8. Summary of statistically significant results from questions related to rewarding data practices. Blue indicates a result greater than the average of the reporting statistic for each question; red indicates a result less than the average. Darker shades indicate larger deviation from the average. Options where career stages did not show statistically significant differences are not shown.

Additionally, a significant difference was observed when it came to assessing the reach and influence of their data as well as other people's data. ECRs found this to be more important than the other groups, while LCRs found it less important.

Connected to this finding, when it comes to the importance of having specific metrics to track their own and others' data, significant differences were observed between the career stages. For every option related to others' data, early career researchers were the group who found it the most important to have metrics available, while LCRs found it the least (see Figure 9). When it comes to metrics on their own data, MCRs were the group who found it the most important to have the metrics available for data citations, data downloads, data views, information on who had used their data, and recognition outside the scholarly system, while early career researchers were the group who found it the most important to have metrics on where data was used and descriptions or narratives on how the data was used (see Figure 10). Notably, LCRs found it the least important to have any of these metrics.

Figure 9. Summary of statistically significant results from questions related to specific metrics to track others' data. Bars are arranged around the middle (50.0% mark) of the 'neither important nor unimportant' category.

Figure 10. Summary of statistically significant results from questions related to specific metrics to track their own data. Bars are arranged around the middle (50.0% mark) of the ‘neither important nor unimportant’ category.

5. Discussion

A general observation can be made that between the four groups of researchers studied as part of this survey (ECRs, MECRs, MLCRs, LCRs), there was a great deal of overlap between the groups. As noted, for the majority of the questions we asked (61.0%), no significant differences were found between the career stages. Additionally, of the 34 questions that had significant differences, 14 (41.0%) of these observations came from just 2 questions’ sub-questions (regarding rewarding and assessing data for reuse or tracing purposes- discussed in section 4.4). As such, it is fair to say that regardless of career stage, researchers have similar views and behaviors towards data sharing and reuse.

For the questions that did have significant differences, it is worth mentioning that there was mostly a directional trend to the results. This is to say that within the 4 groups, if a significant difference was observed, as we went from earlier to later categories the behaviors and attitudes increased or decreased as such (i.e., ECRs thought knowing the number of views data received was the most important, LCRs thought it was the least). As such, this has made the middle career

stages difficult to categorize as distinct, as they are typically a type of mix between the ECRs and LCRs.

5.1. Early career researchers

Our study shows that early career stage researchers are less likely to share their data, connecting to some of the previous findings on this subject (Abele-Brehm et al., 2019; Chawinga & Zinn, 2019; Tenopir et al., 2011; Zhu, 2020). As noted above, the literature on this subject was mixed as some research had found that ECRs shared their data more (Campbell et al., 2019; Nicholas et al., 2020; Zuiderwijk & Spiers, 2019). However, as this survey was a study of researchers from across disciplines, the reason why the patterns are different from these studies is that they looked exclusively at disciplines like astronomy or ecology (where ECRs are sharing more data in general).

When it comes to citing data, ECRs are less likely to say they cite data and, if they do reuse data, are the least likely to include the citation in the reference list. Reasons for ECRs not to cite data were that they were either not aware of where they can find the data that will be relevant to their research (31.6%) or didn't know how to give credit for data they reuse (26.5%). This finding may hint towards the fact that they have less experience in their research area, and are thus not as familiar with this information that is crucial to reusing data. An important component to improving early career research use of data citations and reuse may be incorporating education on the subject into programs for ECRs (i.e., Master and Ph.D. programs).

While sharing data less, our study shows that ECRs find more importance than other researchers in having metrics about others' data. These metrics appear to be important to ECRs in evaluating whether they will reuse a dataset. Perhaps this is related to generational differences, as younger people have grown up in a world with social media and daily life metrics (e.g., likes on photos) (Lupton, 2016). For them, it might be important not only to have these metrics as a way of evaluating their own work but also the relevance of other people's work.

5.2. Mid-career researchers

Mid-career researchers made up the majority of the participants of our study (both MECRs and MLCRs). Despite being such a large group, it was also observed that the mid-career research stage was also a relative blind spot in previous literature on the subject. Not much research has been conducted specifically studying the behaviors and attitudes of mid-career researchers on data sharing and reuse. This study may help explain this phenomenon to some degree, as these individuals are actually placed somewhere between the ECRs and LCRs.

For many of the questions for which a statistically significant difference was determined, a directional pattern was observed. This is to say that ECRs were at one end while LCRs were at the other. Mid-career researchers often fell between the two, with MCRs landing closer to early career researchers and MLCRs landing closer to LCRs. It appears that researchers gradually shift from one position to another throughout their careers, and MCRs are somewhere between the various positions. This makes sense, as when researchers are in the middle of their careers, they have already been accustomed to the systems and norms, which may influence their perceptions and make them more closely connected to LCRs.

A notable exception to this observed pattern was observed for the question regarding obtaining metrics about their own data. MECRs and MLCRs found some of these metrics to be more important compared to the other career stages. This could serve as an indication that in their mid-career, researchers care more about having metrics and evidence on how their work has influenced others to support their tenure promotion (Abele-Brehm et al., 2019; Tenopir et al., 2015). However, it is interesting to note that while researchers may hold the perspective that this is important information to have, data metrics (specifically, citations) are, in fact, almost never considered in tenure promotion (Alperin et al., 2020).

5.3. Late career researchers

LCRs were the most likely to share their data as well as reuse their own data. These findings were consistent with previous literature on the data sharing and reuse by career stages (Chawinga & Zinn, 2019; Dorta-González et al., 2021; Khan et al., 2023; Linek et al., 2017). This makes

sense as with more experience and more time in academic systems, LCRs have had more opportunities to create, share and reuse their data. Additionally, with more time in their career, LCRs will also have had the opportunity to expand their networks and thus have more peers with whom they can exchange data. As some have mentioned before (Dorta-González et al., 2021), LCRs, due to their seniority, see less benefit in keeping their data private than ECRs, possibly due to the job security acquired at this stage of their career.

It appears LCRs follow some of the more established practices of citing data. For example, they were the group that was the most likely to cite the source of data, which is a practice also influenced by disciplinary norms (Gregory, Ninkov, Ripp, et al., 2023). Conversely however, LCRs also seem to be adopting practices that are more traceable when it comes to referring to data. For example, when they cite data, they are the group most likely to cite it in the reference list. This is important because citing data in this way makes it traceable, for researchers but also for scientometric studies.

When it comes to newer ideas on data and data sharing (e.g., treating data as a research output, writing data papers), the LCRs were less likely to engage in these practices. For example, LCRs were found to want others to cite a data paper the least. Data papers are a relatively newer concept that are only taken up (or exist) in certain disciplines, and perhaps as such LCRs were less inclined to want their data referenced in this way. Furthermore, and perhaps most importantly, LCRs found metrics of both their and others' data to be the least important to have available compared to the other career stages. This finding replicates previous findings on the subject as well (Dorta-González et al., 2021).

5.4. Conclusion and future work

Further work is needed to better contextualize the results of this study. First, more work on understanding ECRs is essential. This tends to be an elusive category of researchers that is hard to reach and therefore understand. A limitation of this work was that we were only able to include corresponding authors as potential participants in the survey. As such, the early career research stage was likely underrepresented. The development of different strategies to reach this group and understand their views and behaviors is important for continuing this work.

Additionally, aside from reaching ECRs, there is a need to better understand and quantify the progression that researchers take throughout their career. In this study, career stages were divided into four categories, as a result of previous work and thoughtful foresight before the research began. However, it is still difficult to evaluate the results for these groups as it is not entirely clear of their professional context. The development of improved ways to categorize researchers by their career stage is thus needed to understand the nuanced differences we have reported in this study. For example, mid-career was especially challenging to understand and contextualize. Perhaps in future work asking for academic status (i.e., using phd, postdoc, pre tenure etc...) would be more helpful in the analysis than years of professional experience.

An important finding in this study is that most researchers seem to want to track how their own and other's data was being used, by whom and for what purpose, in the sense that they want to have metrics and contextual information about data reuse. This is especially true for ECRs. In order to generate these metrics, community standards for how data is cited or referenced in articles and publications are essential. Given the findings of this study, a standard practice for this is lacking. Perhaps more targeted outreach to the specific career stages is needed to help unify the behaviors of researchers when it comes to reusing and sharing data. Also, the practices for how we track the ways in which researchers credit data reuse is in a state of transformation with the release of the Data Citation Corpus which compiles mentions of data in the full text in addition to extracting data citations from reference lists (Istrate et al., 2022). It is likely that we will see changes in behavior regarding data reuse as methods for tracking data reuse change.

With adoption of standards and greater metadata coverage, the behaviors and practices we explored in this survey could be more adequately evaluated. Future research will interview researchers directly to complement our understanding of the behaviors and practices observed in this study. These interviews will help shed an interesting light on individual motivations and barriers to data reuse practices. For preliminary results see (Gregory, Ninkov, Roblin, et al., 2023). Furthermore, the influence of the career stage variable could be better assessed in the context of a longitudinal cohort study, where data citation practices could be analyzed in light of changes in career stages. This type of study would also make it possible to see if other variables

influence data citation practices over the course of a career, such as biological age or peer influence.

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Competing interests statement

We have no competing interests to declare.

Data availability

The cleaned and anonymized survey data is published in the Zenodo repository under a CC-BY 4.0 license. A citation to the data set (Ninkov et al., 2023) is listed in the reference list.

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